

DEEP LEARNING FOR NEUTRINO PHYSICS

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History

1958

Perceptron

1986

First neural net used in neutrino experiments
([SNO-STR-96-001](#))

1996

2012

Breakthrough in computer vision
(AlexNet)

2016

First convolutional neural net used in neutrino experiments (NOvA)

2020

Start of the “Neutrino Physics and Machine Learning” (NPML) conference series

[Virtual \(2020\)](#)

[Boston \(2023\)](#)

[Zurich \(2024\)](#)

[Tokyo \(2025\)](#)

2026

+100 research papers on deep learning in neutrino experiments!

Backpropagation popularised

The Nobel Prize in Physics 2024

Convolutional neural net in NOvA

- NuMI Off-axis ν_e Appearance (NOvA) is a long-baseline neutrino oscillation experiment.
 - Measures the neutrino signal close to its source, at Fermilab, as well as 810 km away, at Ash River, MN.
- Pioneering on using convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for neutrino identification (2016).
 - *A. Aurisano et al, "A Convolutional Neural Network Neutrino Event Classifier", [arXiv:1604.01444v3](https://arxiv.org/abs/1604.01444v3).*
 - Aim to identify particle interactions in sampling calorimeters.

- The NOvA CNN classifier outperformed any other algorithms in use by the NOvA collaboration!

DUNE DEEP UNDERGROUND NEUTRINO EXPERIMENT

- International neutrino oscillation experiment in the USA.
- Far detectors located 1300 kilometres away from the source.
- More than 1500 collaborators from +200 institutions in +30 countries.
- Goal: measuring CP violation.

www.dunescience.org/

- DUNE Far detector data (LArTPCs):
 - The Far Detectors contain three wire readout planes.
 - This provides three “images” of each neutrino interaction (500x500 pixels each).

Convolutional neural network in DUNE

Results

- The flavour identification results are used in the official analysis of DUNE:
 - [arXiv:2002.03005](https://arxiv.org/abs/2002.03005).
 - <https://doi.org/EPJC/S10052-020-08456-Z>.
- Sensitivity to CP violation:

- 5σ after seven years of data collection.
- A milestone for the experiment!
- Made possible thanks to the convolutional neural network.

Understanding the CNN

- Occlusion tests:
 - Hide parts of the images and check how the CNN reacts to the changes.

electron neutrino (ν_e)

Removing the start of the electron shower reduces the ν_e score, as expected

muon neutrino (ν_μ)

The CNN finds the vertex a bit ambiguous, but it is using the end point of the muon to gain a handle on the event type.

Deep learning on sparse data

- Only a bunch of pixels contain relevant information (dark blue pixels mean literally “empty”).
 - ~99% of the pixels are empty.
- “Standard” state-of-the-art methods in computer vision (CNNs, ViTs) are designed for dense images.
 - Loads of useless computation.
 - Models tend to “learn” about empty patterns.
- Submanifold Sparse Convolutional Networks (SSCNs) perform the convolution **operation only on the non-zero elements of the data**, resulting in an efficient and accurate representation of the data.

– ~16 times faster than standard CNNs on neutrino data!

(arxiv.org/abs/2303.08812).

– Open source frameworks:
MinkowskiEngine, **spconv**.

- Other used architectures:
 - Graph neural networks.
 - PointNets.
 - Transformers.

Graph neural nets in neutrino physics

1. SuperFGD node classification ([PhysRevD.103.032005](#))

Node-level tasks

Predict a label, type, category, or attribute of a node.

E.g. detect fake accounts in a large social network with millions of users.

Edge-level tasks

Given a set of nodes and an incomplete set of edges between these nodes, infer the missing edges.

E.g. predict the probability that a user will be interested in a product.

Graph-level tasks

Carry a classification, regression, or clustering task over entire graphs.

E.g. predict molecules' toxicity based on the graph representing the structure of a molecule

2. LArTPC particle aggregation ([PhysRevD.104.072004](#))

3. IceCube event classification ([10.1109/ICMLA.2018.00064](#))

[[Source](#)]

Combining methods

- End-to-end deep-learning chain for LArTPC neutrino reconstruction using particle interaction images as input (github.com/DeepLearnPhysics/spine):

SPINE

[arXiv:2102.01033](https://arxiv.org/abs/2102.01033)

Sparse U-Nets for identifying clusters, track vs shower...(semantic segmentation).

[10.1103/PhysRevD.104.032004](https://arxiv.org/abs/10.1103/PhysRevD.104.032004)

GNNs for grouping objects into particles, particle identification...

[10.1103/PhysRevD.104.072004](https://arxiv.org/abs/10.1103/PhysRevD.104.072004)

T2K

- T2K (Tokai to Kamioka) is an international neutrino oscillation experiment in Japan.

More than 500 collaborators from 80 institutions in 12 countries.

- SuperFGD: main upgrade to the near detector.

JINST 13 (2018) 02, P02006
NIM A936 (2019) 136-138

2D
projections

3D
reconstruction

- 2M optically independent cubes, 1 cm³ per cube.
- Spatial localisation of scintillation light.

Deep learning in the near detector

90% of the noise is eliminated without harming the signal.

[doi/10.1103/PhysRevD.103.032005](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevD.103.032005)

~95% accuracy!

Deep learning in the near detector

[nature.com/articles/s42005-023-01239-4](https://www.nature.com/articles/s42005-023-01239-4)

[nature.com/articles/s42005-024-01669-8](https://www.nature.com/articles/s42005-024-01669-8)

More deep learning in T2K!

A. Chalumeau at EPS-HEP 2025.

- PointNet for identifying EM showers:

- Vision transformer for PID:

Row-normalized (True Label)

True label	electron	gamma	muon	pion	proton
electron	0.85	0.022	0.03	0.096	0.0043
gamma	0.11	0.79	0.012	0.059	0.028
muon	0.021	0.006	0.78	0.18	0.0096
pion	0.055	0.019	0.2	0.68	0.047
proton	0.0062	0.019	0.013	0.093	0.87
Predicted label	electron	gamma	muon	pion	proton

T2K preliminary

Fully integrated into T2K analysis level software

Hyper-Kamiokande

- **Start:** Hyper-K begins operation in 2028.
- **Scale:** $\sim 8\times$ larger fiducial mass than Super-K.
- **Leptonic CPV reach:** sensitivity for $\delta_{CP} \approx 6-20^\circ$ (depends on the true value of δ_{CP}).
- **Mass ordering:** $\sim 4-6\sigma$ sensitivity, depending on $\sin^2\theta_{23}$.
- **Graph neural network for event classification:**

[B. Quilain at NPML2025 \[Link\]](#)

[E. Le Blévec at NPML2025 \[Link\]](#)

- **Vision Transformer for event reconstruction:**

[S. Chen at NPML2025 \[Link\]](#)

- Vertex.
- Direction.
- Momentum

- Experiment at CERN's Large Hadron Collider designed to search for light, weakly interacting particles and study high-energy neutrinos produced in proton-proton collisions.

- **FASERCal** is a proposed upgrade for FASER.

- 3D precision calorimeter for high-energy neutrinos.
- Inspired by the SuperFGD detector at T2K.
- Goals: detecting CC ν_e and CC ν_μ interactions, measuring differential cross-sections and identifying charm and tau events.
- ETH Zürich is leading its design.

[A. Mascellani at FASER Run 4 Workshop](#)

Simulated ν_μ CC interaction in 3DCal modules : reconstructed 3D voxels

Neutrinos with energies up to the TeV scale!

Masked pre-training using a transformer encoder:

Work in progress!

Fine-tuning of the pre-trained model:

Classification output:

- $\text{prob}(\nu_e \text{ CC}), \text{prob}(\nu_\mu \text{ CC}), \text{prob}(\text{NC}), \text{prob}(\nu_\tau \text{ CC})$
- $\text{prob}(\text{charm})$

Regression output:

- Visible momentum vector P_{vis}
- Hadronic jet momentum vector p_{jet}

New detector concept: PLATON (R&D)

- R&D project at ETH Zurich (SNSF Grant PCEFP2_203261).
 - Goal: **plenoptic system** on top of an unsegmented plastic scintillator block to achieve **sub-millimetre spatial resolution** of particle tracks.
 - Plenoptic cameras: capture "light field" for depth imaging, but designed for intensity-based scenes.
 - Sensors are **single-photon avalanche diode arrays** (SPADs).
 - Details: [arXiv:2511.09442](https://arxiv.org/abs/2511.09442).

3D reconstruction in PLATON

- Developed a (non-ML) ray tracing method.
 - Tested on single tracks.
 - Depth resolution: 3 mm.
 - Lateral resolution: 0.9 mm.
 - [arXiv:2511.09442](https://arxiv.org/abs/2511.09442)
- Goal to scale to complex neutrino interactions:

Detected photons

Event

Algorithm

3D reconstruction

Deep-learning reconstruction

[arXiv:2511.09442](https://arxiv.org/abs/2511.09442)

- Using a **transformer-encoder** (inspired by Google's BigBird):
 - Attention mechanism correlates all the photons.
 - Sparse attention: linear $O(n)$ instead of quadratic $O(n^2)$ complexity!
 - Successfully trained on events with thousands of photons.
 - Combination of MSE and Chamfer distance as loss.
 - Training MC sample supported by prototype data!**

Deep learning results

<200 μm resolution!

[arXiv:2511.09442](https://arxiv.org/abs/2511.09442)

- Also tested on out-of-distribution events (trained on neutrino interactions only):

It seems to have learnt the optics!

Summary

- Deep learning has the potential to revolutionise neutrino physics, enabling precise event reconstruction and physics analyses.
- Transformers, graph, and sparse convolutional networks have been deployed across multiple neutrino experiments (DUNE, T2K, Hyper-K, FASERCal).
- Interpretability techniques (e.g., occlusion tests) help build trust in ML-driven analyses.
- Novel detector concepts (e.g., plenoptic systems) are pushing the boundaries of 3D reconstruction.

Credit: ChatGPT

Prompt: “Studying neutrino interactions with AI in London”

Credit: Gemini

Prompt: “Studying neutrino interactions with AI in London”

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